

Topology Optimization and Manufacturing of 3D Architected Composites Using Additive Fiber Tethering

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Adoption of Continuous Fiber Reinforced Thermoset Composites

- Continuous load path offers superior mechanical performance
- Tailorable anisotropic properties
- Better temperature stability

Short fiber reinforced

Continuous fiber reinforced

Fabrication Challenge of Topology Optimized Composite Bracket

- Traditional composite manufacturing in fabrication of smaller parts are challenged with
 - Limited flexibility in fiber orientation
 - Difficulty in producing complex 3D geometries
 - Material and process inefficiency

- Bracket - GE metal AM challenge

- Can not utilize continuous fiber orientation
- Limited by layer adhesion

- Conventional composites can't fabricate such optimized geometries utilizing the continuous fiber orientation

3D Printing Inspired Continuous Reinforcement for Bracket

CAD model

.STL conversion

Continuous fiber

Tessellation (triangulated)

Topology optimization and beam conversion

Goal and Constraints for the Bracket

Goal:

- Develop topology optimization and manufacturing process for 3D continuous fiber composites
- Explore 3D composites potential applications

Requirements:

- Continuous carbon fiber, thermoset resin
- NO joining
- Mechanical performance (see below)

Load conditions 1 Static Vertical 8000 lbs up			
Load conditions 3 Static 42 degrees from vertical 9500 lbs out			
Load interfaces 			

Additive Fiber Tethering (AFT) Fabrication Framework

Bracket design and topology optimization

Fiber Path Planning for AFT

Fiber path planning:

Hierholzer algorithm illustration

Hierholzer algorithm provides:

- **Continuous fiber path generation** for continuous carbon fiber reinforcement
- **Node graph planning** with previously deposited fiber paths.

Modified Hierholzer algorithm for AFT

Modified Hierholzer algorithm integrates:

- **Spatial constraints** such as physical fiber bending limits.
- **Avoid collision risks** with previously deposited fiber paths.

Fiber Path Planning for AFT

Additive Fiber Tethering fabrication:

Scaffold for bracket

0.30 lbs

AFT fabrication

Characterization of the Bracket

Vacuum bagging with salt:

TGA analysis:

Optical analysis of cross sections:

Sample	Fiber Volume Fraction (%)
Vacuum bagging with salt sample	50.9
Pristine sample	41.9

Mechanical Characterization of the Bracket

Tensile testing:

Load conditions 1

Static

Vertical

35.59 kN up

Tensile performance of the bracket

Crosshead rate: 0.05 in/min

Other Potential Applications

Bike frame

Drone frame

Engine bracket

Stool

3DFit Drone Frame
Drop impact test

Drone frame drop test

Exhibition Highlights: ARPA-E Summit

ARPA-E Summit 2025:

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